

THE ISSUE OF THE HISTORY OF TEACHING MOTHER TONGUE AND LITERARY SCIENCE IN EASTERN MADRASAS

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Abstract: In this article, scientific-theoretical comments are made about the teaching system of social humanitarian sciences, especially mother tongue and literary sciences, and methodological possibilities of educational literature taught as textbooks in the madrasas of Turkestan, especially in Bukhara.

Key words: Madrasah, "science of distribution", "science of distribution", geometry, arithmetic, textbooks, teaching materials for geography, "malumatul afoq", medical information, "shifoul qulub", etc.

According to historical literature, some changes were made in the field of education in Bukhara in the XVII-XVIII centuries. During the reign of Amir Shahmurad (1785-1800), culture, literature, and youth education were somewhat developed, but during the reign of his son Amir Haydar (1800-1826), science, culture, including education in schools, were neglected. The rest Old knowledge in the field of history education was given in madrasahs, history lessons were taught based on "History of Iskandari" by an unknown author and "History of the world" by Alauddin Otamalik Juvaini (1236-1283). As a result of the study of the sources of that time, it was found that theology and law were taught based on the knowledge of the VIII-IX centuries. Depending on the wishes of the students, they additionally studied the works of some Persian poets and learned oriental medicine, and elementary knowledge of arithmetic, algebra, and geometry was given in addition to the curriculum.

Madrasa students studied in three stages. There were no tests to pass from one stage to another, but after mastering certain textbooks, they moved on to others. Madrasahs required students to master approximately 137 textbooks on philosophy and law to complete a full course. After all, classes in schools and madrasas were conducted in Arabic and Persian languages.

In the madrasas under the control of the Kokhan Khanate, textbooks related to geometry and arithmetic, such as "Ilmi Faroiz", "Taksim ilmi" were used. Educational materials related to geography were taught from books such as "malumatul afoq", and information about medicine was taught from books such as "shifoul qulub". The works of some thinkers and scientists are also taught. In contrast to boys' schools, more attention is paid to studying the works of classical poets. Also, there are special aspects of girls' education, such as "tealimi

banot" of Ali Nazima, who teaches them about housekeeping, cooking, cleanliness, oriental manners, "the manners of communication" of Alimat ul-Banot, "family" of Fakhriddin ibn Rizauddin, " textbooks such as tarbiyali khatun" were used. Starting from 1917, the Russian language was also taught in schools and madrasas. This year, the number of Russian-language schools in Uzbekistan reached 160. In Muslim schools, the age and mental characteristics of students are not taken into account. At the same time, children of different ages were taught in one room. Enlightened pedagogue Sadriddin Ainiy remembers the old school and writes that it was very narrow and dark, the light came only from the cracks in the door, a mat was used instead of the floor, and it was very cold in winter were. Books such as "Haftiyak", "Chor kitab", "Sufi Olloyar", "Tajvid", "Farzi ayn", "Qur'an" chapters and verses, "Devoni Fuzuli", "Devoni Bedil", "Devoni Amir Navoi" are available in schools and madrasas. and poetry collections were taught. In this regard, modern enlighteners Abdulla Avloni, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Haji Muin, Munavvargori Abdurashidkhanov emphasize that these educational works are not suitable for children's age and contradict their spiritual world, therefore, it is necessary to urgently reform the textbooks and manuals in schools and the educational system. they count. In 1905, the efforts of the enlighteners gave their results. Only after this year, the educational system of schools was somewhat reformed. The results of the study of available scientific historical sources and archival materials showed that at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, a socio-political and pedagogical need arose in Turkestan to create textbooks in the Turkish (now Uzbek) language. This need was explained by the need to accelerate the process of national awakening by increasing the literacy of the country's population.

1. First, as a result of the policy of making the people of the country literate and awakening the national consciousness, and secondly, as a result of the policy of Russification, many different types of schools were opened, and the movement to provide these educational institutions with textbooks was widespread.
2. Due to the urgent need to meet the huge need for textbooks in schools, the creation and publication of textbooks has risen to the level of state policy.
3. In order to implement the policy of Russification of the Turkic peoples as an ideological and educational weapon - education, representatives of the state belonging to the Russian nationality began to lead the movement of providing schools with textbooks.

4. Uzbek intellectuals not only took an active part in opening new schools and creating textbooks, but also published them at their own expense.

Ibrat's book "lug'ati sitta al-sina" ("six-language dictionary") was published in Tashkent in 1901 at the publishing house of Ilin. It consists of 53 pages. The dictionary consists of two parts, in which more than a thousand words are explained. Before Ibrat, M.Nalivkina compiled dictionaries "Russian-Sartovskiy Slovar" and "Sartovsko-Russkiy Slovar", from which it was somewhat more difficult to learn the Russian language. She was the first Uzbek to create an exemplary dictionary.

In conclusion, the teaching of social and humanitarian sciences and the creation of textbooks related to this field in the Eastern countries have gone through various stages of development.

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